

Exploring Women in the Workplace: Overcoming Challenges and Achieving Success in Pakistan's Corporate Sector

Farah Kainat¹, Sahar Iftikhar²

¹ Lecturer, Institute for Art and Culture Riawand Road Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan

² Assistant Professor, Institute for Art and Culture Riawand Road Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan

Corresponding Author's Email: farah.kainat@iac.edu.pk

Accepted: 15 December 2023, Received in Revised form: 20 November 2023, Published: 26 December 2023

Abstract

This research delves into the challenges faced by women in achieving professional success in Pakistan, examining the complex interplay of cultural, religious, and socio-economic elements. It pinpoints major hindrances such as the misinterpretation of religious doctrines concerning the role of women, deep-seated cultural stereotypes, and pervasive patriarchal views. A significant obstacle identified is "Sifarish" (favoritism and nepotism), which hinders fair career advancement. The study underscores the lackluster execution of legislative measures designed to aid women in their professional lives, underscoring the necessity for more resolute efforts from both government and corporate entities. The suggested remedies involve collaborating with religious scholars to rectify misconceptions about women's roles in religious texts and initiating public awareness campaigns to dismantle stereotypes. The research demonstrates the beneficial impacts of women's employment on their personal lives and family dynamics, in addition to broader economic gains such as increased GDP and societal progress.

Keywords: Woman Workplace, Challenges, Corporate Sector, Pakistan

Introduction

The role of women in entrepreneurship as a catalyst for economic development has been extensively explored in various studies, such as those by Tunio et al. (2021a) and Ge et al. (2022). However, the complexity and diversity of women's experiences in the entrepreneurial realm have prompted significant scholarly inquiry. Ge et al. (2022) highlighted how certain research and discourse in female entrepreneurship inadvertently reinforce gender-based subordination. The dynamic corporate environment of Pakistan is increasingly recognizing the critical role and representation of women in leadership. This shift is pivotal in the broader discourse on gender equality and the efficacy of organizational structures. Globally, there has been a significant movement towards gender inclusivity in leadership roles, yet in Pakistan, women in the corporate sector confront distinct challenges and barriers on their path to leadership. This research paper delves into these obstacles, the progress made to date, and the enduring gaps in the ascent of Pakistani women to leadership roles within the corporate milieu. These approaches often cast women entrepreneurs as pivotal for economic growth, yet simultaneously evaluate them against dominant male-centric business standards deemed crucial for entrepreneurial success. Tunio et al. (2021a) argue that such evaluations lead to the "women under-performance hypothesis," which rather than questioning these established norms, attempts to rationalize why women underperform based on various metrics.

The corporate sector in Pakistan, mirroring global trends, has traditionally been male-dominated. This is a reflection of deep-seated cultural norms, societal expectations, and ingrained organizational practices that have historically impeded women's career progression. Nonetheless, emerging global research increasingly underscores a direct link between diversity in leadership, particularly gender diversity, and the overall success of organizations. This connection necessitates a reevaluation of the role of women within Pakistan's corporate hierarchy. For a thorough understanding of how female entrepreneurship can spur economic growth, it's imperative to delve into its gendered dimensions (Tunio et al., 2021b; Asghar et al., 2020). In Pakistan, particularly, women encounter considerable hurdles in accessing economic opportunities, leading to a significant disparity in business ownership rates between men and women. A Global Entrepreneurship report in 2021 revealed that women's business ownership rate stands at a mere 1.6 compared to men's 5.81. This backdrop underscores the necessity of understanding the specific challenges that women in Jamshoro district face as they venture into business, leveraging both traditional and contemporary skills.

Central to this study is an exploration of the diverse and complex barriers that Pakistani women encounter in their professional journey. These challenges span societal and cultural expectations, entrenched organizational biases, and the often difficult balance between professional responsibilities and personal life. Furthermore, the paper scrutinizes how these challenges are being tackled at both policy levels and within the fabric of corporate culture. Consequently, this research primarily aims to shed light on the challenges that young local women encounter in entering the business world in Jamshoro district. The study focuses on identifying the barriers and hurdles female entrepreneurs face and how they maneuver through these challenges to establish and maintain their businesses.

The outcomes of this study are anticipated to enhance the understanding of the challenges and opportunities inherent in female entrepreneurship in Pakistan. The findings will be invaluable for policymakers, educators, and business support organizations, assisting them in crafting and executing effective strategies to bolster women's involvement in entrepreneurship. Furthermore, this research will add to the wider dialogue on gender and entrepreneurship, emphasizing the need to acknowledge and address the gender-specific norms and practices that perpetuate inequality in this sector. The essence of this research is twofold: it aims not only to identify the barriers faced by Pakistani women in the corporate sector but also to shed light on the success stories, effective strategies, and policies that facilitate women's leadership roles in Pakistan. In doing so, the study contributes to the ongoing conversation about gender diversity in leadership, providing valuable insights and recommendations relevant to corporations, policy makers, and aspiring female leaders in Pakistan and beyond.

Literature Review

The increasing prominence of women in leadership roles across the globe is extensively documented. The pivotal study by Eagly and Carli (2007), titled "Through the Labyrinth," intricately outlines the myriad of obstacles women encounter on their journey to leadership positions. This research is instrumental in shaping our understanding of the broader global landscape in which Pakistani female leaders find themselves. Focusing on Pakistan, the corporate environment poses distinct challenges for women in leadership roles. Ali and Kramar's 2015 study delves into the impact of cultural and social norms on career progression for women in Pakistan,

pinpointing critical hurdles like entrenched gender stereotypes and insufficient family support. Their research is key to comprehending the specific nuances of female leadership within the Pakistani context. The issue of the 'glass ceiling' remains a pivotal topic in discussions about female leadership. Javaid and Shafi's 2019 research addresses this phenomenon within the context of Pakistani organizations, identifying the subtle, often unseen barriers that inhibit women from attaining senior leadership roles.

Khan et al.'s 2020 research takes a closer look at how the practices of Pakistani companies affect the representation of women in leadership roles. Their study indicates that organizational policies and practices can significantly influence — either positively or negatively — the advancement of women into leadership positions. The link between gender diversity in leadership and organizational performance has sparked considerable debate. A crucial study by Hoobler et al. in 2018 demonstrates that higher gender diversity in senior management teams is associated with improved organizational performance. This finding is especially pertinent in the context of Pakistan's corporate sector. Recent efforts to foster women's leadership development in Pakistan have also been the subject of scholarly research. Mahmood and Shah's 2021 study critically assesses these initiatives, providing valuable insights into effective strategies and identifying areas where improvements are needed in the Pakistani setting.

In the last thirty years, the realm of female entrepreneurship has seen a marked increase in scholarly interest and research. Originating with early papers in the 1970s, the field has since diversified, embracing a wide range of disciplines, methodologies, and geographical focuses (Asghar et al., 2020; Memon et al., 2018). A critical aspect of this research involves comprehending the profiles and aspirations of female entrepreneurs, particularly in Asia. Recent studies, such as those by Anderson et al. (2021), reveal that despite underestimation, female entrepreneurs are driven by a strong desire to demonstrate their capabilities through hard work, persistence, and determination. The contribution of educated women in leadership roles to the entrepreneurial landscape has garnered increasing recognition. Studies, including those by Carter et al. (2017), highlight the pivotal role female leaders play in offering support, guidance, and mentorship to women entrepreneurs. Díaz-García et al. (2015) observed that women in leadership positions are instrumental in fostering gender equality in their organizations, potentially enhancing the presence and success of female entrepreneurs. Moreover, research indicates that female leaders often adopt collaborative and participative leadership styles, spurring innovation and creativity within their organizations (Gupta & Shukla, 2020; Wang et al., 2018). They are also more inclined to emphasize social responsibility and ethical practices, contributing to their organizations' reputations and sustainable growth (Kaliannan et al., 2019).

In terms of scale, female-led startups, especially in low-income Asian countries, are typically smaller regarding employees, revenue, and profit. Women entrepreneurs tend to be more risk-averse and face limitations in building external networks (Gilal et al., 2020). In Asia, many women engage in entrepreneurship within the informal sector, often in traditional markets with lower incomes. This trend is partly due to the concentration of women in lower-status occupations and limited access to technical training and salaried positions, which restricts their entrepreneurial potential (Ab Hamid et al., 2014). Societal norms and gender expectations can significantly impede women's entrepreneurial success. Studies by Qureshi et al. (2018) and Shah et al. (2016) highlight how these factors shape female entrepreneurial identities and influence their achievements. Additionally, women's empowerment is often overlooked, further limiting their entrepreneurial

prospects (Ali & Zardari, 2023).

In many Asian contexts, a husband's career is frequently deemed more important, which can constrain opportunities for female entrepreneurs (Lambert, 2021; Raza et al., 2018). Despite these hurdles, female entrepreneurs in Asia continue to exhibit resilience and determination in surmounting obstacles and establishing successful ventures. Consequently, the study of female entrepreneurship in Asia has evolved, focusing on the unique challenges these women face and their impact on economic growth. While significant barriers exist, recent research, including that by Chowdhury et al. (2018), underscores the resolve and resilience of female entrepreneurs in overcoming these challenges. To further encourage female entrepreneurship in Asia, it is essential for policymakers, educators, and business leaders to address the societal and gender norms impeding women's success and to create more supportive environments for female entrepreneurs to flourish.

Material and Methods

Choosing an appropriate research methodology and framework that aligns with the research questions and context is crucial (Hair, 2010). For our study, which aims to delve into the complex experiences of Pakistani women in the workplace, an interpretive qualitative method was employed (Saunders et al., 2012). This approach is particularly effective for gaining a deep understanding of specific situations and environments (Cresswell, 2003). Our exploratory study aimed to amplify the voices of women, shedding light on their meanings and interpretations (Creswell, 2013). Unlike quantitative methods, qualitative research provides in-depth insights into the beliefs and processes underpinning a phenomenon (Bryman, 2004), allowing for a thorough exploration of various contextual factors that may affect it (Bryman et al., 1996).

Conducting research with female participants in conservative, patriarchal societies presents unique challenges. Given the difficulties in acquiring samples through standard methods, we resorted to convenience and snowball sampling techniques (Berg et al., 2004). The goal was not to create a random or representative sample, but rather to identify individuals knowledgeable about the process (Hornby and Symon, 1994, p. 169). The snowball method was employed to enable participants to recommend other potential respondents (Atkinson and Flint, 2001). To mitigate the risk of sample bias inherent in snowball sampling, where initial participants might refer people similar to themselves (Biernacki and Waldorf, 1981), we initiated five separate snowball chains starting from diverse networking sources in different industries: banking, telecommunications, healthcare, education, and food.

Participants were reached via phone calls and emails to inform them about the research purpose. Prior to data collection, all participants were assured of adherence to appropriate standards of data retention, confidentiality, and ethics. Informed written consent was obtained from all participants before data collection commenced. To protect participant anonymity, no identifying information was included in the manuscript, and participants were referred to using letters (A, B, C, etc.) instead of their names.

In our study, data was gathered through in-depth, semi-structured interviews, a method aligned with qualitative research principles (Creswell, 2013). We conducted seven detailed interviews, structured based on guidelines from Abalkhail (2017) and modified to suit the needs of our investigation. While following this structure, we remained open to exploring additional themes

brought up by participants. Probing questions were occasionally introduced to guide discussions towards the study's core objectives. Interviews were conducted via various mediums - face-to-face, over the phone, WhatsApp, and Skype - and each lasted between 40 and 75 minutes. The majority were video calls, enabling us to observe non-verbal cues, crucial for enriching qualitative data, especially in sensitive topics like gender disparity (Sturges and Hanrahan, 2004). Four interviews were in English, while the others were in Urdu, later translated to English by bilingual experts. To encourage candid responses, interviews weren't recorded, but detailed notes were meticulously taken.

There were no significant issues with misunderstandings or misinterpretations, as the interviewer, assistants, and participants shared similar gender, socio-religious, and cultural backgrounds. To enhance the study's rigor, precision, and credibility, we employed various techniques such as triangulation (Patton, 1999), confirmability (Shenton, 2004), and member checks (Mertens, 2014). Investigator triangulation involved multiple researchers in data collection, offering diverse observations and conclusions, enriching the study's depth (Carter et al., 2014). Member checks involved verifying interview summaries with participants to ensure accuracy in representing their views.

For data analysis, each respondent was treated as a unique case. Notes were taken immediately post-interview to retain critical insights. Adopting the methods recommended by Miles and Huberman (1994) and Braun and Clarke (2006), we conducted a thorough thematic analysis. This involved multiple readings of the transcripts, developing a coding scheme focusing on workplace challenges and gender equality issues. Codes were continuously refined through analytic induction. Main themes were identified and aligned with existing literature, ensuring coherence and relevance.

The use of NVivo 14 Plus facilitated the thematic analysis, helping identify and map the emerging relationships between themes (King, 2004). Finally, themes were theoretically integrated, and connections were drawn in relation to the research questions, culminating in a comprehensive understanding of the workplace challenges and barriers as perceived by the participants.

Results and Discussion

The analysis revealed themes and subthemes spanning personal, organizational, and socio-cultural dimensions, each intricately linked and affecting women's career progression in Pakistan. These themes, reflecting interconnections across micro, meso, and macro levels, highlight the complex nature of the challenges faced by working women in Pakistan.

The findings underscored a prevailing belief among Pakistani women that national socio-economic and cultural contexts significantly influence their career trajectories. A common challenge identified was the misinterpretation of religious texts regarding women's roles, leading to entrenched stereotypes about women earning a living. Many women pointed out how cultural norms are often wrongly ascribed to religious teachings, hindering their professional growth.

For instance, Ms. A from the banking sector remarked, "Islam advocates ease and doesn't restrict women's professional endeavors. If mutually agreed, dual earning is perfectly acceptable in Islamic teachings." Similarly, Ms. B from the education sector observed, "Old misconceptions still persist. Some men believe women should only focus on domestic responsibilities, confusing cultural practices with religious dictates, thereby limiting women's work opportunities."

Another theme was the concept of "Sifarish" (favoritism and nepotism). Almost all participants

expressed frustration towards this widespread practice, which they felt disproportionately disadvantaged women due to their limited access to influential networks. Ms. B from academia highlighted, "Sifarish undermines merit, posing a greater challenge for women who generally lack the extensive networks that men have."

Moreover, respondents pointed out that despite legislative reforms aimed at improving working conditions for women, these measures often fall short in practice due to a lack of accountability and enforcement. Ms. P, a manager in the education sector, commented, "Many organizations treat legislative reforms as mere formalities, with little real impact on women's career advancement due to poor accountability." The participants suggested several interventions to improve women's career prospects. They emphasized the need for effective government action in enforcing legislation and holding organizations accountable. Ms. C from the banking sector stated, "There's a gap between policy and practice. Regular oversight and feedback from government authorities could help bridge this gap by ensuring policy implementation."

More than half of the participants also recommended engaging religious scholars to clarify misconceptions about women working. They suggested using media platforms to disseminate accurate religious teachings and counteract the stereotypes stemming more from tradition than religion. An associate professor expressed, "The government should engage progressive Islamic scholars to correct misinterpretations of religious texts used to justify male dominance, thereby enlightening society about the true essence of Islamic teachings regarding women and work."

All the women interviewed highlighted that achieving career equality and enhancing female participation in the workforce would significantly contribute to poverty reduction. Ms. D, employed in a telecom call center, shared her personal experience, "Coming from a conservative, lower-class family, I wasn't initially allowed to work, despite being more educated than my husband. With five children and my husband's unstable job, we struggled financially. Once we decided that I should also work, our financial situation improved considerably, leading to a happier life."

A gender studies expert, Ms. C, emphasized the broader socio-economic impact: "In Pakistan, a large segment of the population is either below the poverty line or belongs to the lower middle class. With the rise in women's education, translating this into higher workforce participation could dramatically reduce poverty. Households with dual earners generally enjoy a higher income and better quality of life. Countries with greater female workforce participation have seen increases in their GDP and productivity, benefiting from a diverse workforce. Another key benefit discussed was happiness and improved quality of life. A bank employee, Ms. A, reflected on her experience: "Before I started working, our financial constraints caused a lot of stress, negatively affecting my behavior at home. Since I've been employed, our quality of life has significantly improved, I'm much happier, and my relationship with my children is better, despite some time and energy constraints. Similarly, Ms. E from the banking sector shared, "I've always been independent and confident. Post-marriage, not being able to work due to traditional modesty expectations led to depression and deteriorating health. Returning to work restored my health, confidence, and happiness. My job is a source of competitiveness, independence, and a key factor in my well-being."

Themes

- Distorted interpretation of religious doctrine concerning female roles and modesty, highlighting how misconceptions about religious teachings affect women's professional lives.
- Societal norms and traditions constraining women's career paths, examining how societal expectations limit professional opportunities for women.
- Dominance of patriarchal thought, focusing on the widespread patriarchal attitudes impacting women's career advancement.
- "Sifarish" impact (favoritism and nepotism), looking at how favoritism and nepotism obstruct women's progress based on merit.
- Deficiencies in enforcing and upholding gender-supportive legislation, exploring the gaps in applying and monitoring laws meant to bolster women in the workforce.
- Mandating accountability in gender equality law enforcement, emphasizing the need for more stringent government and corporate responsibility in applying gender equality statutes.
- Engagement with religious authorities for clarification on work-related religious guidelines, suggesting the involvement of religious scholars to demystify religious teachings about women's employment and dispel prevalent misunderstandings.
- Concrete measures for actualizing existing gender policies, highlighting the importance of taking actionable steps to put gender policies into practice effectively.
- Enhanced life quality and familial harmony for working women, providing insight into how employment positively affects women's personal well-being, stress levels, and family relationships, along with boosting self-esteem and mental health.
- Economic growth through diverse workforce inclusion, analyzing how female participation in the workforce contributes to increased GDP and overall economic development.
- Societal advantages of female empowerment and inclusion, underscoring the broader social gains that come from embracing gender inclusivity and empowering women.

Findings

The study reveals a complex web of challenges hindering the professional progress of women in Pakistan. Central to these is the misinterpretation of religious doctrines, leading to deeply ingrained societal misconceptions about women's roles and expectations of modesty. These issues are compounded by cultural stereotypes and the pervasive influence of patriarchal norms, which further limit women's career opportunities. The widespread practice of "Sifarish," a form of favoritism and nepotism, disrupts fair career advancement. Furthermore, legislative efforts intended to support women in the workplace are often poorly implemented and lack proper oversight, underscoring the urgent need for more accountable government and corporate actions. The study suggests engaging religious scholars to help reinterpret and disseminate accurate religious perspectives on women's employment, thereby challenging and changing existing beliefs. Additionally, it highlights the positive effects of female employment, noting improvements in women's quality of life and mental well-being, enhanced family relationships, and significant contributions to economic growth, including increases in GDP, stemming from a more diverse and inclusive workforce.

Conclusion

The study's conclusion draws attention to the complex challenges Pakistani women face in their professional lives, primarily due to the misinterpretation of religious scriptures, deep-seated cultural norms, and prevailing patriarchal views. These challenges are further intensified by the practice of "Sifarish," which obstructs fair career progression based on merit. The research stresses the importance of effectively applying and enforcing legal reforms to aid women's professional development, calling for increased accountability from both government and corporate sectors. It also suggests engaging religious scholars to correct and spread authentic religious perspectives on women's employment. Importantly, the study sheds light on the beneficial effects of women's participation in the workforce on their personal satisfaction, family life, and wider economic measures like GDP enhancement. It demonstrates that empowering women professionally is not just beneficial for their individual lives but also plays a crucial role in the broader social and economic progress, underlining the need for more inclusive and supportive employment environments.

Practical and Theoretical Implications

The outcomes of this study are crucial for shaping the actions of policymakers and corporate leaders in Pakistan. There is an urgent requirement for more robust enforcement and application of laws pertaining to gender equality in the workplace. This involves not just revising legal frameworks but also cultivating an organizational culture that truly values and integrates these changes, moving beyond superficial compliance. Addressing the entrenched practice of 'Sifarish', or favoritism, is another critical step, potentially through establishing transparent and merit-based hiring and promotion practices. Additionally, companies are encouraged to create more inclusive environments, perhaps by offering flexible work schedules or childcare support, to boost female workforce participation. On a wider scale, the findings advocate for a collaborative approach between the government and religious scholars to correct misunderstandings of religious doctrines related to women's roles, using media channels to disseminate accurate information and dismantle longstanding cultural biases. Implementing these measures can lead to a more balanced workplace, contributing positively to the country's social and economic fabric.

From a theoretical perspective, this research adds valuable insights to the body of knowledge on gender inequality in the workplace, particularly spotlighting the complex mix of cultural, religious, and socio-economic elements in Pakistan. It challenges conventional models that tend to neglect the specific circumstances of developing nations like Pakistan, where the interplay of religion and culture significantly affects workplace norms. The findings indicate that theoretical approaches to gender equality in the workplace must account for these specific cultural and religious contexts, particularly in environments where gender roles are heavily influenced by religious misinterpretation and cultural traditions. Moreover, the study extends the discussion on the role of 'Sifarish' in work environments, suggesting an expansion of existing organizational behavior and human resource management theories to encompass these unique socio-cultural factors. This approach not only broadens the scope of current theoretical frameworks but also opens new research pathways to devise more tailored theories and models that effectively address the unique challenges women face in the workforce in similar cultural contexts.

Recommendations

This research proposes a variety of key actions to improve the inclusion of women in Pakistan's workforce. Strengthening and effectively enforcing legal provisions for gender equality, alongside establishing accountability measures for organizations, is crucial. It is important to rectify cultural and religious misinterpretations by engaging with religious scholars and leveraging media platforms for educational initiatives, which will help dismantle entrenched stereotypes and biases. An essential step is to eradicate the 'Sifarish' culture, advocating for transparent and merit-based practices in hiring and promotions. Moreover, the adoption of supportive policies that facilitate work-life balance, such as flexible work schedules, remote work opportunities, and childcare support, is recommended. These measures are geared towards fostering a more inclusive and fair work environment, thereby advancing gender equality and contributing to the wider societal and economic progress in Pakistan.

References

1. Abalkhail, J. M. (2017). Women and leadership: challenges and opportunities in Saudi higher education. *Career Dev. Int.* 22, 165–183. doi: 10.1108/cdi-03-2016-0029.
2. Abalkhail, J. M., and Allan, B. (2015). Women's career advancement: mentoring and networking in Saudi Arabia and the UK. *Hum. Resour. Dev. Int.* 18, 153–168. doi: 10.1080/13678868.2015.1026548.
3. Acker, J. (1999). "Rewriting class, race, and gender: problems in feminist rethinking," in *Revising Gender*, eds M. M. Ferree, J. Lorber, and B. B. Hess (Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage), 44–69.
4. Acker, J. (2009). From glass ceiling to inequality regimes. *Sociol. Trav.* 51, 199–217. doi: 10.1016/j.soctra.2009.03.004
5. Adame, C., Capliure, E. M., and Miquel, M. J. (2016). Work–life balance and firms: a matter of women? *J. Bus. Res.* 69, 1379–1383.
6. Adler, N. (2015). "Women leaders: shaping history in the 21st century," in *Women as Global Leaders*, eds F. W. Ngunjiri and S. R. Madsen (Charlotte, NC: Information Age Publishing), 21–50.
7. Aguirre, D., Hoteit, L., Rupp, C., and Sabbagh, K. (2012). *Empowering the Third Billion: Women and the World of Work in 2012*. McLean, VA: Booz and Company.
8. Ahonen, P., Tienari, J., Meriläinen, S., and Pullen, A. (2014). Hidden contexts and invisible power relations: a Foucauldian reading of diversity research. *Hum. Relat.* 67, 263–286. doi: 10.1177/0018726713491772
9. Al-Asfour, A., and Khan, S. A. (2014). Workforce localization in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: issues and challenges. *Hum. Resour. Dev. Int.* 17, 243–253. doi: 10.1080/13678868.2013.836783
10. Al-Asfour, A., Tlaiss, H. A., Khan, S. A., and Rajasekar, J. (2017). Saudi women's work challenges and barriers to career advancement. *Career Dev. Int.* 22, 184–199. doi: 10.1108/cdi-11-2016-0200.
11. Alhejji, H., Ng, E. S., Garavan, T., and Carbery, R. (2018). The impact of formal and informal distance on gender equality approaches: the case of a British MNC in Saudi Arabia. *Thunderbird Int. Bus. Rev.* 60, 147–159. doi: 10.1002/tie.21828.
12. Al-Hibri, A. Y. (2000). *An Introduction to Muslim Women's Rights*. Syracuse, NY: Syracuse University Press.
13. Ali, F. (2013). A multi-level perspective on equal employment opportunity for women in Pakistan. *Equal. Divers. Incl.* 32, 289–309. doi: 10.1108/edi-12-2012-0110.
14. Ali, F., and Knox, A. (2008). Pakistan's commitment to equal employment opportunity for women: a toothless tiger? *Int. J. Employ. Stud.* 16, 39–58.
15. Ali, M., Kulik, C. T., and Metz, I. (2011). The gender diversity–performance relationship in services and manufacturing organizations. *Int. J. Hum. Resour. Manag.* 22, 1464–1485. doi: 10.1080/09585192.2011.561961

16. Alimo-Metcalfe, B. (2010). Developments in gender and leadership: introducing a new “inclusive” model. *Gend. Manag. Int. J.* 25, 630–639. doi: 10.1108/17542411011092291.
17. Al-Qur’an (39:9). Chapter 39, Sura-e-Az Zumar. Verse 9.
18. Al-Qur’an (96:1–5). Chapter 96, Sura-e-Al Alašq. Verses 1–5.
19. Alvesson, M., and Sköldbberg, K. (2009). *Reflexive Methodology: New Vistas for Qualitative Research*. London: Sage.
20. Antelo, A. A. (2015). *She Figures 2015*. Brussels: European Commission.
21. Atkinson, R., and Flint, J. (2001). Accessing hidden and hard-to-reach populations: snowball research strategies. *Soc. Res. update* 33, 1–4.
22. Balchin, C. (1996). *Women, Law and Society: An Action Manual for NGOs (Women Living Under Muslim Laws, Women and Law, Pakistan Country Project)*. Lahore: Shirkat Gah.
23. Barsh, J., and Yee, L. (2012). *Unlocking the Full Potential of Women at Work*. New York, NY: McKinsey & Company.
24. Baumeister, R. F., Campbell, J. D., Krueger, J. I., and Vohs, K. D. (2003). Does high self-esteem cause better performance, interpersonal success, happiness, or healthier lifestyles? *Psychol. Sci. Public Interest* 4, 1–44. doi: 10.1111/1529-1006.01431
25. BBC News (2015). Are Pakistan’s Female Medical Students to be Doctors or Wives?
26. Beller, A. H. (1982). Occupational segregation by sex: determinants and changes.
27. *J. Hum. Resour.* 17, 371–392.
28. Berdahl, J. L., and Moore, C. (2006). Workplace harassment: double jeopardy for minority women. *J. Appl. Psychol.* 91, 426–436. doi: 10.1037/0021-9010.91.2.426
29. Berg, B. L., Lune, H., and Lune, H. (2004). *Qualitative Research Methods for the Social Sciences, Vol. 5*. Boston, MA: Pearson.
30. Bianchi, S. M., and Milkie, M. A. (2010). Work and family research in the first decade of the 21st century. *J. Marriage Fam.* 72, 705–725. doi: 10.1111/j.1741-3737.2010.00726.x
31. Biernacki, P., and Waldorf, D. (1981). Snowball sampling: problems and techniques of chain referral sampling. *Sociol. Methods Res.* 10, 141–163. doi: 10.1177/004912418101000205
32. Blau, F. D., and Beller, A. H. (1988). Trends in earnings differentials by gender, 1971–1981. *ILR Rev.* 41, 513–529. doi: 10.1177/001979398804100402
33. Braun, V., and Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qual. Res. Psychol.* 3, 77–101. doi: 10.1191/1478088706qp063oa
34. Broadbridge, A. (2008). Senior careers in retailing. *Gend. Manag. Int. J.* 23, 11–35. doi: 10.1108/17542410810849105
35. Brough, P., and O’Driscoll, M. P. (2010). Organizational interventions for balancing work and home demands: an overview. *Work Stress* 24, 280–297. doi: 10.1080/02678373.2010.506808
36. Bryman, A. (2004). Qualitative research on leadership: a critical but appreciative review. *Leadersh. Q.* 15, 729–769. doi: 10.1016/j.leaqua.2004.09.007
37. Bryman, A., Stephens, M., and Campo, C. (1996). The importance of context: qualitative research and the study of leadership. *Leadersh. Q.* 7, 353–370. doi:10.1016/s1048-9843(96)90025-9
38. Cain, M., Khanam, S. R., and Nahar, S. (1979). Class, patriarchy, and women’s work in Bangladesh. *Popul. Dev. Rev.* 5, 405–438.
39. Carter, N., Bryant-Lukosius, D., DiCenso, A., Blythe, J., and Neville, A. J. (2014). The use of triangulation in qualitative research. *Oncol. Nurs. Forum* 41, 545–547.
40. Cooke, F. L. (2001). Equal opportunity? The role of legislation and public policies in women’s employment in China. *Women Manag. Rev.* 16, 334–348. doi: 10.4103/1658-354X.159476
41. Cresswell, J. (2003). *Research Design: Quantitative and Mixed Mode Approaches*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
42. Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches*.

- Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
43. Cunningham, R. B., and Sarayrah, Y. K. (1993). *Wasta: The Hidden Force in Middle Eastern Society*. Westport, CT: Praeger Publishers.
 44. Derks, B., Ellemers, N., Van Laar, C., and De Groot, K. (2011). Do sexist organizational cultures create the Queen Bee? *Br. J. Soc. Psychol.* 50, 519–535. doi: 10.1348/014466610X525280
 45. Derks, B., Van Laar, C., and Ellemers, N. (2016). The queen bee phenomenon: why women leaders distance themselves from junior women. *Leadersh. Q.* 27, 456–469. doi: 10.1016/j.leaqua.2015.12.007
 46. Diekmann, A. B., and Eagly, A. H. (2008). “Of men, women, and motivation,” in *Handbook of Motivation Science*, eds J. Y. Shah and W. L. Gardner (New York, NY: The Guilford Press), 434–447.
 47. Eagly, A., and Carli, L. (2007). *Through the Labyrinth: The Truth about How Women Become Leaders*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.
 48. Eagly, A. H. (2013). “Women as leaders: leadership style versus leaders’ values and attitudes,” in *Gender and Work: Challenging Conventional Wisdom*, eds R. J. Ely and A. J. C. Cuddy (Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press), 4–11.
 49. Eagly, A. H., and Karau, S. J. (2002). Role congruity theory of prejudice toward female leaders. *Psychol. Rev.* 109, 573–598. doi: 10.1037//0033-295x.109.3.573
 50. Eagly, A. H., and Wood, W. (2011). Feminism and the evolution of sex differences and similarities. *Sex Roles* 64, 758–767. doi: 10.1007/s11199-011-9949-9
 51. Elder, S., and Smith, A. (2010). *Women in Labour Markets: Measuring Progress and Identifying Challenges*. Geneva: International Labour Office.
 52. Ellemers, N., Van den Heuvel, H., De Gilder, D., Maass, A., and Bonvini, A. (2004). The underrepresentation of women in science: differential commitment or the queen bee syndrome? *Br. J. Soc. Psychol.* 43, 315–338. doi: 10.1348/0144666042037999
 53. Fakhr, Z., Dal Bianco, S., and Bilal, S. (2016). Pricking the male bubble in academia – exploration of female academic experiences in a number of Pakistan universities. *Zarządzanie Publiczne* 4, 369–377.
 54. *Frontiers in Psychology* | www.frontiersin.org 16 June 2019 | Volume 10 | Article 1376 Sarwar and Imran Multi-Level Career Prospects of Pakistani Women
 55. Francoeur, C., Labelle, R., and Sinclair-Desgagné, B. (2008). Gender diversity in corporate governance and top management. *J. Bus. Ethics* 81, 83–95. doi:10.1007/s10551-007-9482-5
 56. GGGR (2017). *Global Gender Gap Report*. World Economic Forum. Cologny/Geneva.
 57. Ghouse, S. M., Mcelwee, G., Meaton, J., and Durrah, O. (2017). Barriers to rural women entrepreneurs in Oman. *Int. J. Entrepreneurial Behav. Res.* 23, 998–1016.
 58. Goheer, N. (2003). *Women Entrepreneurs in Pakistan: How to Improve their Bargaining Power*, InFocus Programme on Boosting Employment through Small Enterprise Development. Geneva: International Labour Office.
 59. Hair, J. F. (2010). *Multivariate Data Analysis*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
 60. Hakim, C. (2000). *Work-Lifestyle Choices in the 21st Century: Preference Theory*. Oxford: OUP.
 61. Hennekam, S., Tahssain-Gay, L., and Syed, J. (2017). Contextualising diversity management in the Middle East and North Africa: a relational perspective.
 62. *Hum. Resour. Manag. J.* 27, 459–476. doi: 10.1111/1748-8583.12150
 63. Hodges, J. (2017). Cracking the walls of leadership: women in Saudi Arabia. *Gend. Manag. Int. J.* 32, 34–46. doi: 10.1108/gm-11-2015-0106
 64. Hodgson, G. M. (2006). What are institutions? *J. Econ. Issues* 40, 1–25.
 65. Hofstede, G. (2001). *Culture’s Consequences: Comparing Values, Behaviors, Institutions and Organizations Across Nations*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
 66. Holden, N., Michailova, S., and Tietze, S. (eds). (2015). *The Routledge Companion to Cross-Cultural Management*. London: Routledge.
 67. Holvino, E. (2010). *Intersections: the simultaneity of race, gender and class in organization studies*.

- Gend. Work Organ. 17, 248–277. doi: 10.1111/j.1468-0432.2008.00400.x
68. Hornby, P., and Symon, G. (1994). “Tracer studies,” in *Qualitative Methods in Organizational Research, A Practical Guide*, eds C. Cassell and G. Symond (London: Sage).
69. Ibn Maja in Al-Sunan (1:18). Vol. 1, Book 1, Hadith 224 Islam, N. (2004). Sifarish, sycophants, power and collectivism: administrative culture in Pakistan. *Int. Rev. Adm. Sci.* 70, 311–330. doi: 10.1177/0020852304044259
70. Jacobs, J. A. (1992). Women’s entry into management: trends in earnings, authority, and values among salaried managers. *Adm. Sci. Q.* 37, 282–301.
71. Jain, H., Lawler, J., Bai, B., and Lee, E. (2010). Effectiveness of Canada’s employment equity legislation for women (1997–2004): implications for policy makers. *Relat. Industrielles* 65, 304–329.
72. Jejeebhoy, S. J., and Sathar, Z. A. (2001). Women’s autonomy in India and Pakistan: the influence of religion and region. *Popul. Dev. Rev.* 27, 687–712. doi: 10.1111/j.1728-4457.2001.00687.x
73. Joshi, A., Neely, B., Emrich, C., Griffiths, D., and George, G. (2015a). Gender research in AMJ: an overview of five decades of empirical research and calls to action. *Acad. Manag. J.* 58, 1459–1475. doi: 10.5465/amj.2015.4011
74. Karam, C. M., and Afiouni, F. (2014). Localizing women’s experiences in academia: multilevel factors at play in the Arab Middle East and North Africa. *Int. J. Hum. Resour. Manag.* 25, 500–538. doi: 10.1080/09585192.2013.792857
75. Kassem, F. S. (2012). Can women break through? Women in municipalities: Lebanon in comparative perspective. *Womens Stud. Int. Forum* 35, 233–255. doi: 10.1016/j.wsif.2012.04.002
76. Kelly, E., and Dobbin, F. (1999). Civil rights law at work: sex discrimination and the rise of maternity leave policies. *Am. J. Sociol.* 105, 455–492. doi: 10.1086/210317
77. Kemp, L. J., and Madsen, S. R. (2014). Oman’s labour force: an analysis of gender in management. *Equal. Divers. Incl. Int. J.* 33, 789–805.
78. Khalaf, R. (2017). This is how Islam led the World with Women’s Rights. Step feed.
79. Kiaye, R. E., and Singh, A. M. (2013). The glass ceiling: a perspective of women working in Durban. *Gend. Manag. Int. J.* 28, 28–42. doi: 10.1108/17542411311301556
80. King, N. (2004). “Using templates in the thematic analysis of text,” in *Essential Guide to Qualitative Methods in Organizational Research*, Vol. 2, eds C. Cassell and G. Symon (London: SAGE), 256–270. doi: 10.4135/9781446280119.n21
81. Klasen, S., and Pieters, J. (2015). What explains the stagnation of female labor force participation in urban India? *World Bank Econ. Rev.* 29, 449–478. doi:10.1093/wber/lhv003
82. Kossek, E. E., and Lautsch, B. A. (2012). Work–family boundary management styles in organizations: a cross-level model. *Organ. Psychol. Rev.* 2, 152–171. doi: 10.1177/2041386611436264
83. Kossek, E. E., and Michel, J. S. (2011). *Flexible Work Schedules*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
84. Kossek, E. E., Su, R., and Wu, L. (2016). “Opting Out” or “Pushed Out”? Integrating perspectives on women’s career equality for gender inclusion and interventions. *J. Manag.* 43, 228–254. doi: 10.1177/0149206316671582
85. Krishnan, H. A., and Park, D. (2005). A few good women: on top management teams. *J. Bus. Res.* 58, 1712–1720. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2004.09.003
86. Leonard, J. F. (1986). “The effectiveness of equal employment law and affirmative action regulation,” in *Research in Labor Economies*, ed. R. G. Ehrenberg (Greenwich, CT: JAI Press), 319–350.
87. Lippa, R. A. (2005). *Gender, Nature, and Nurture*. London: Routledge.
88. Loko, M. B., and Diouf, M. A. (2009). *Revisiting the Determinants of Productivity Growth: What’s New?* (No. 9-225). Washington, DC: International Monetary Fund.
89. Loots, S., and Walker, M. (2015). Shaping a gender equality policy in higher education: which human capabilities matter? *Gend. Educ.* 27, 361–375. doi:10.1080/09540253.2015.1045458

91. Madsen, S. R., and Scribner, R. T. (2017). A perspective on gender in management. *Cross Cult. Strateg. Manag.* 24, 231–250.
92. Martins, L. L., Eddleston, K. A., and Veiga, J. F. (2002). Moderators of the relationship between work-family conflict and career satisfaction. *Acad. Manag. J.* 45, 399–409. doi: 10.5465/3069354
93. McKinsey Global Institute (2017). *Women Matter. Time to Accelerate Ten Years of Insights into Gender Diversity.*
94. Mernissi, F. (2011). *Beyond the Veil: Male-Female Dynamics in Muslim Society.* London: Saqi Books.
95. Mertens, D. M. (2014). *Research and Evaluation in Education and Psychology: Integrating Diversity with Quantitative, Qualitative, and Mixed Methods.* Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage publications.
96. Metcalfe, B. (2007). Gender and human resource management in the Middle East. *Int. J. Hum. Resour. Manag.* 18, 54–74. doi: 10.1080/09585190601068292
97. Miles, M. B., and Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative Data Analysis: An Expanded Sourcebook.* Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
98. Mullally, S. (1995). *Women and Employment Legislation in Pakistan: a Review.* Lahore: British Council Pakistan.
99. Ng, E. S., and Sears, G. J. (2017). The glass ceiling in context: the influence of CEO gender, recruitment practices and firm internationalization on the representation of women in management. *Hum. Resour. Manag. J.* 27, 133–151. doi: 10.1111/1748-8583.12135
100. Nielsen, M. W. (2016). Gender inequality and research performance: moving beyond individual-meritocratic explanations of academic advancement. *Stud. High. Educ.* 41, 2044–2060. doi: 10.1080/03075079.2015.1007945
101. Nielsen, M. W. (2017b). Scandinavian approaches to gender equality in academia: a comparative study. *Scand. J. Educ. Res.* 61, 295–318. doi: 10.1080/00313831.2016.1147066
102. Özbilgin, M. F. (2006). Relational methods in organization studies: a review of the field. *Relat. Perspect. Organ. Stud. Res. Companion* 244.
103. Özbilgin, M. F., Syed, J., Ali, F., and Torunoglu, D. (2012). International transfer of policies and practices of gender equality in employment to and among Muslim majority countries. *Gend. Work Organ.* 19, 345–369. doi: 10.1111/j.1468-0432.2010.00515.x
104. Patton, M. (2002). *Qualitative Research and Evaluative Methods.* London: Sage. Patton, M. Q. (1999). Enhancing the quality and credibility of qualitative analysis. *Health Serv. Res.* 34(5 Pt 2), 1189–1208.
105. Pio, E., and Syed, J. (2013). Our bodies, our minds, our men: working South Asian women. *Gend. Manag. Int. J.* 28, 140–150. doi: 10.1108/gm-01-2013-0006
106. Powell, G. N., and Greenhaus, J. H. (2010). Sex, gender, and decisions at the family? work interface. *J. Manag.* 36, 1011–1039. doi: 10.1177/0149206309350774
107. Rehman, S., and Azam Roomi, M. (2012). Gender and work-life balance: a phenomenological study of women entrepreneurs in Pakistan. *J. Small Bus. Enterp. Dev.* 19, 209–228. doi: 10.1108/14626001211223865
108. Roller, M. R., and Lavrakas, P. J. (2015). *Applied Qualitative Research Design: A Total Quality Framework Approach.* New York, NY: Guilford Publications.
109. Sarwar, F., and Abbasi, A. S. (2013). An in-depth analysis of women's labor force participation in Pakistan. *Middle East J. Sci. Res.* 15, 208–215.
110. Saunders, M., Lewis, P., and Thornhill, A. (2012). *Research Methods for Business Students,* 6th Edn. Harlow: Financial Times Prentice Hall.
111. Schwabenland, C., and Tomlinson, F. (2015). Shadows and light: diversity management as phantasmagoria. *Hum. Relat.* 68, 1913–1936. doi: 10.1177/0018726715574587
112. Scott, W. R. (2014). *Institutions and Organizations: Ideas, Interests, and Identities,* 4th Edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

113. Scott-Jackson, W., Kariem, B., Porteous, A., and Harb, A. (2010). Maximising Women's Participation in the GCC Workforce'. Oxford: OSC Gulf.
114. Shenton, A. K. (2004). Strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects. *Educ. Inf.* 22, 63–75. doi: 10.3233/efi-2004-22201
115. Smith, N., Smith, V., and Verner, M. (2006). Do women in top management affect firm performance? A panel study of 2,500 Danish firms. *Int. J. Prod. Perform. Manag.* 55, 569–593. doi: 10.1108/17410400610702160
116. Staines, G., Tavis, C., and Jayaratne, T. E. (1974). The Queen Bee syndrome. *Psychol. Today* 7:55.
117. Sturges, J. E., and Hanrahan, K. J. (2004). Comparing telephone and face-to-face qualitative interviewing: a research note. *Qual. Res.* 4, 107–118. doi: 10.1177/1468794104041110
118. Syed, J., and Ali, F. (2013). Contextual emotional labor: an exploratory of Muslim female employees in Pakistan. *Gend. Manag. Int. J.* 28, 228–246. doi: 10.1108/gm-01-2013-0007
119. Syed, J., Ali, F., and Hennekam, S. (2018). Gender equality in employment in Saudi Arabia: a relational perspective. *Career Dev. Int.* 23, 163–177. doi: 10.1108/cdi-07-2017-0126
120. Syed, J., Ali, F., and Winstanley, D. (2005). In pursuit of modesty: contextual emotional labor and the dilemma for working women in Islamic societies. *Int. J. Work Organ. Emot.* 1, 150–167.
121. Syed, J., and Özbilgin, M. (2009). A relational framework for international transfer of diversity management practices. *Int. J. Hum. Resour. Manag.* 20, 2435–2453. doi: 10.1080/09585190903363755
122. Tanaka, S., and Muzones, M. (2016). Policy Brief on Female Labor Force Participation in Pakistan, (ADB Briefs No. 70). Metro Manila: Asian Development Bank.
123. Terjesen, S., Aguilera, R. V., and Lorenz, R. (2015). Legislating a woman's seat on the board: institutional factors driving gender quotas for boards of directors. *J. Bus. Ethics* 128, 233–251. doi: 10.1007/s10551-014-2083-1
124. Theodorakopoulos, N., and Budhwar, P. (2015). Guest editors' introduction: diversity and inclusion in different work settings: emerging patterns, challenges, and research agenda. *Hum. Resour. Manag.* 54, 177–197. doi: 10.1002/hrm.21715
125. Timberlake, S. (2005). Social capital and gender in the workplace. *J. Manag. Dev.* 24, 34–44. doi: 10.1108/02621710510572335
126. Tlaiss, H., and Kauser, S. (2010). Perceived organizational barriers to women's career advancement in Lebanon. *Gend. Manag. Int. J.* 25, 462–496. doi: 10.1108/17542411011069882
127. Tlaiss, H., and Kauser, S. (2011). The importance of wasta in the career success of Middle Eastern managers. *J. Eur. Ind. Train.* 35, 467–486. doi: 10.1108/03090591111138026
128. Turcotte, M. (2011). Women and Education: Women in Canada: a Gender Based Statistical Report. (accessed November 12, 2018).
129. UN Women (2016). Annual Report, 2016–2017. New York, NY: UN Women. Van Oosten, E. B., Buse, K., and Bilimoria, D. (2017). The leadership lab for women: advancing and retaining women in STEM through professional development. *Front. Psychol.* 8:2138. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2017.02138
130. Varela, A. F. (2018). These are the Countries with Worst Gender Pay Gaps. New York, NY: Business Insider Espana.
131. Weyer, B. (2007). Twenty years later: explaining the persistence of the glass ceiling for women leaders. *Women Manag. Rev.* 22, 482–496. doi: 10.1108/09649420710778718
132. Williams, J. (2000). *Unbending Gender: Why Family and Work Conflict and what to do about it.* Oxford: Oxford University Press.
133. Winchester, H. P. M., and Browning, L. (2015). Gender equality in academia: a critical reflection. *J. High. Educ. Policy Manag.* 37, 269–281. doi:10.1080/1360080x.2015.1034427
134. Women's Human rights and gender equality (2017). Available at: <http://www.ohchr.org/EN/Issues/Women/WRGS/Pages/WRGSIndex.aspx> (accessed April 1, 2019).

doi: 10.1080/1360080x.2015.1034427

135. Wood, W., and Eagly, A. H. (2009). "Gender identity," in Handbook of Individual Differences in Social Behavior, eds M. Leary, and R. Hoyle (New York, NY: Guilford Press), 109–125.
136. World Bank (2016). Women, Business and the Law. [Electronic Resource]. Available at: <http://www.worldbank.org>
137. World Economic Forum (2014). The Global Gender Gap Report 2014. Geneva: World Economic Forum.
138. Zaroni, P., Janssens, M., Benschop, Y., and Nkomo, S. (2010). Guest editorial: unpacking diversity, grasping inequality: rethinking difference through critical perspectives. *Organization* 17, 9–29. doi: 10.1177/1350508409350344